

Clustering for Impact: Lessons learned from #AllAtlantic Cluster

*Recommendations to EC REA and future HorizonEU & FP10 applicants
on strategies and mechanisms for agile clustering of parallel project portfolios*

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Cover Image: The Pleiades also known as the Seven Sisters, is collection of young stars formed from the same cloud, and the *most obvious star cluster to the naked eye* (Source: NASA Hubble Space Telescope)

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Disclaimer: The following recommendations to EC are based on experiments and experiences since 2013 entirely within Horizon2020 Societal Challenge FOOD and HorizonEU Global Challenge 5 & 6, in support of #GalwayStatement, #BelenStatement and the current #AAORIA #AllAtlantic Ocean Research & Innovation Alliance. Lessons learned and recommendations are framed to be relevant to any part of the HorizonEU Pillar II Global Challenges Clusters.

CLUSTERING FOR SOCIETAL IMPACT

Recommendations to EC REA and future HorizonEU & FP10 applicants on strategies and mechanisms for agile clustering of parallel project portfolios

Context: “Clustering” of projects **at all scales** (within the same Topic, across topics under the same Societal Challenge, and across Horizon Pillars) has been explicit priority in Framework Programmes for at least a decade. Degree of expected clustering from the beneficiaries side, has varied from unclear to highly prescriptive across Societal (and later Global) Challenges, resulting in diverse but vague interpretations of how “clustering” should be correctly put in practice.

“We could have done much more, had we allocated a task to work together”

**TechOCEANS
Coordination
Team**

“A framework for how a portfolio ‘cluster’ should work, would be beneficial”

**EuroSEAS
Coordination
Team**

While Horizon 2020 Societal Challenge “Secure, Clean & Efficient Energy” expected regularly beneficiaries to dedicate a WP or a Task to cluster with relevant concurrent projects at EU and national levels, Societal Challenges “Food Security” and “Climate Action” expectations were mostly unclear, or occasionally pointing to a single, specific parallel Call.

This was the case in HorizonEU Work Programmes, until WP2025 when Topic drafting started to change, in parallel to the compilation of this Policy Brief.

Opportunity: More than 64% of the “marine research” budget in 2025-2027 is locked in Topics funding more than one project. As this rises, the possibility of duplication and/or missed opportunities not detected at evaluation also increases. As the burden on evaluation committees grows, there is a clear need for systematic solutions for parallel project funded from the same Topic, to explicitly and contractually co-deliver for impact.

Tested example cases below with potential for scalability, demonstrate how multi-project Topics offer systematic opportunities for pooling of resources from pre- to post-award stages: from **co-design** of proposals, **co-creation** with stakeholders pre- and post-award, to **co-delivery** and **joint exploitation** of results (be it towards policy or private sector). This can directly reduce likelihood of duplication of funded work, as well as **reduce stakeholder fatigue** as projects in the same Topic portfolio, if implemented systematically.

Recommendations herein are organized into those relevant **for the funder**, as well as **for future applicants** (the beneficiaries) in HorizonEU and Framework Programme 10. Where the recommendations for the applicants have been tested in funded project(s), reference is made to a specific “**proposal asset**” guiding applicants how to deploy and implement the recommendation in future proposals, and **offer scalability**.

“Policy Briefs should represent the views of a cluster of multiple projects”

**OceanICU
Coordination
Team**

The **#AllAtlantic CLUSTER** of 15+ projects, also offer a “work in progress” definition of “clustering” that may assist dialogue, and/or calibrate expectations for both funders and beneficiaries.

Definition: (*work in progress, for future versions of this brief*) Clustering in the context of HorizonEU Projects is more than just “name dropping” and mapping the landscape of related projects with overlapping R&D objectives. Effective clustering refers to **mapping concurrent projects** with similar objectives, and providing clear, specific, and **dedicated tasks, with meaningful budget** and partner capacities (e.g. “*living bridge partners*” participating in projects to be clustered) and using the full **contractual flexibility** embedded in the legal framework, so that the proposal/project can convincingly co-deliver joint R&D, exploitation activities, collectively reduce stakeholder fatigue, intentionally provoke evidence for early uptake of results.

Scalable Examples

1. EXAMPLE Cooperation with National Science Foundation & NASA (USA)

General experience with supporting Galway Statementⁱ, Belem Statementⁱⁱ and #AORAⁱⁱⁱ between 2010-2020s (via Grant Agreements like FP7-ENV-2010 & [BG-08-2018-2019](#)^{iv}) consistently relied on a strategy of 1) agreeing on high-level priorities, and 2) funding “*own for own*” projects with the aspiration that parallel projects would cluster and collaborate in support of the high-level priorities. This type of fragmented, patchwork funding landscape imposed difficulties and frustrations for those in the community seeking specific and concrete cooperation between parallel projects with overlapping objectives. Barriers included **lack of systematic access to funded projects proposals** to build upon explicitly, **contractual rigidity** of existing funded projects, very **limited contractual options** to divert small funds into emerging opportunities **to cluster projects together**.

2. EXAMPLE RIA-type Projects

Two Sister Projects^v funded out of [H2020-LC-BG-03-2018](#)^{vi} (SUMMER and MEESO, RIAs in direct competition), were **co-designed, co-drafted** and **co-submitted** by the same research community, some of which participated in both funded projects. The “clustering” at drafting stage insured optimal fit and synergy between the two concepts, and final designs, in a way building in contingencies for “**contractual rigidity**” at implementation, a problem encountered frequently when clustering problems. The high level of conceptual synergies between the two proposals meant **minimal duplication of work** from the start, **high evaluation** of both proposals, and **high degree of conceptual complementarity** during implementation. Since the successful implementation, the case has proven relevant and topical with other parallel Topics that funded two projects at a time (e.g. TechOCEANS & Nautilus Projects in [H2020 BG-07-2019-2020](#)).

3. EXAMPLE IA-type Projects

Three Sister Projects proposed in [HorizonEU MISS-2024-OCEAN-01-03](#) collaborated at concept design (IA’s not in direct competition, same Topic objectives targeting 3 different regions). Unlike the “RIA-type Calls Case”, the three sister proposals only openly shared partnerships and Exploitation Strategy, but not the details of the “Excellence” design. The case is useful for optimizing conceptual synergies, **co-demonstration of solutions at high TRL**^{vii} using embedded reserve funds, **co-commercialize** innovation across all regions, and **reducing stakeholder fatigue** on the topic of “bycatch”. As the frequency of multiple project Topics increases, the opportunity for embedding conceptual synergies to underpin effective clustering is significant. **Lack of applicant awareness** of eligible mechanisms at their disposal, is still a major barrier to proactively mobilizing partners to co-design and co-deliver with concurrent consortia. This success story has now funded [ECO-CATCH](#) and [Marine Guardian](#) Projects, and both chair the TRAIID Bycatch Cluster (2025-2030).

4. EXAMPLE #AllAtlantic Ocean Research & Innovation Alliance

Six Sister Projects funded out of [Horizon2020 BG-08-2018-2019](#) directly to support #AAORIA #AllAtlantic Ocean Research & Innovation Alliance, formed the initial monthly cluster at management level. The goal was clustering of SMART objectives, resources, and post-award implementation. **Contractual rigidity** embedded within the project design, and **reluctance to use any existing mechanisms allowing for contractual flexibility**, were frequently barriers to implementing specific joint research & exploitation activities across contracts.

5. EXAMPLE Clustering with Partnerships (BlueBio & Biodiversa+)

Especially on the #AAORIA priority area of “**coastal resilience**”, HorizonEU Partnerships and Calls therein offered a promising mechanism for extending, building upon selected components of #AllAtlantic projects. In the case of BlueBio 2022 Call, #AllAtlantic projects SUMMER & MEESO were explicitly mentioned as examples to build upon. This mobilized the latter consortia to engage the rest of the community, and rapidly communicate promising areas of research, and can help visibly trace the legacy of HorizonEU project through nationally co-funded mechanisms.

The #AllAtlantic CLUSTER of project managers made sustained and repeated efforts to engage both secretariats administering BlueBIO and Biodiversa+, in order to systematically repeat the practice.

The objectives were:

- 1) **offer free advice to applicants** willing to build upon contract we implemented, offer pooling of resources, identify co-financing opportunities,
- 2) **offer access** to Grant Agreements (Part B) where those were not publicly disclosed, to accelerate direct synergies, and
- 3) **offer to future** Partnerships' Calls **examples** of projects to build upon (without influencing prioritization on Partnership Calls).

Contractual rigidity at implementation, and **concerns with respect to independence** of the Partnerships, i.e. entities beyond the Partnerships beneficiaries are seeking to de-nature the prioritization of Call Themes, prevented duplication of the success given above with BlueBIO Call 2022.

6. EXAMPLE Exploitation Plans in general

There is a general concern that Horizon 2020 Consortia left exploitation too late into the average 4 year projects, and even in best cases effective exploitation requires time beyond the average 4 yr project lifetime. This is also recently echoed by EC Court of Auditors Report in the context of emerging AI technology^{viii}.

At least one Horizon 2020 Grant Agreement^{ix} implemented a combination of contractual flexibility through reserve funds, and an extra 12 months after the main R&D deliverable were completed. This clearly allowed the consortium to focus on exploitation alone as a project within the project, devise basic transfer pathways, and engage in the difficult task to dialogue with specific end-users (versus broad range dissemination, and one-way communication).

In addition, for many non-engineering project where the main result is new knowledge, consortia could not have devised a prescriptive and effective Exploitation Strategies 5 yrs prior to holding the tangible Key Exploitable Results (KER) in their collective hands.

Researchers gain significantly more clarity on **“demonstrable benefits for specific end-users that can be causally linked to the outputs of the project”** once the deliverables are finalized, and the scientific caveats fully explored.

... so what does this mean specifically for CLUSTERING in 2026-2027 funded projects ? ...

“proposals should allocate sufficient resources for effective coordination, with concrete cooperation activities to be defined at a later stage”

Source: [HORIZON-CL6-2025-01-BIODIV-05](#), first appears in draft from, Mar-Apr 2025

... and for the next Framework Programme 10 (2028-2034) ? ...

“More flexibility across the budget, so Europe has the capacity to act – and react – fast when circumstances change unexpectedly or when new policy priorities need to be addressed ”

Source: [The 2028-2034 EU budget for a stronger Europe](#)

RECOMMENDATIONS to APPLICANTS:

- a1 **CLUSTER** with past projects, by explicitly extending and building upon specific parts (traceable outputs/deliverables/tasks) of past projects, instead of at overall objective level only;
- a2 **CLUSTER** with specific parts (traceable outputs/deliverables/tasks) of **concurrent proposals**, in the interest of ad-hoc co-delivery, co-dissemination, reducing stakeholder fatigue, reducing demonstration and validation costs, and boosting collective power to reach end-users;
- a3 **CLUSTER** with **multiple concurrent proposals**, when crafting, drafting, and proactively disseminating actionable advice & recommendations in the form of policy-relevant briefs! Stakeholder fatigue is a real problem, and single-project policy messages are a weak conduit for actionable advice;
- a4 **DEPLOY** more proactive clustering instruments (e.g. reserve funds) for more **targeted, specific and purposeful clustering** with concurrent projects, where the joint activities deliver more than the sum of its parts;
- a5 **CLUSTER** with complimentary concurrent projects, following the example of the #AllAtlantic CLUSTER of Project Managers (e.g. 30min per month, with a standing agenda on reducing duplication & stakeholder fatigue, optimizing outreach and impact) as a forum for mutual support to deliver the recommendations above, and as a collective focus on common objectives;
- a6 Consider running distributed **PROPOSAL CLINIQUES** in the closing year of the cluster of projects, to support third party applicants to national and EU R&D funds, that explicitly build on top of the research priorities (and success results!) of your projects! How many “spin-off” R&D applications you can document is an accepted KPI for the legacy of your project;
- a7 **RESERVE FUND^{xi} for joint PhDs** is an eligible and tested mechanism, and can be deployed to **mobilize 50% co-financing by Graduate Schools** within the consortium beneficiaries (easiest option) or beyond consortium (by inviting new beneficiaries in the Consortium after project start)
- a8 **RESERVE FUND for MOBILITY for ECOPs^{xii}** is an eligible and tested mechanism, and can be an effective mechanism for **resolving emerging R&D problems** in the second half of the project lifetime, **clustering** with Sister Projects, matching with existing personal development & secondment funds within HorizonEU non-eligible organizations (e.g. NOAA), **capacity building with the Global South** and developing countries, directly adding value to the Action.
- a9 **RESERVE FUND for EXPLOITATION** (possibly combined with additional 12 months dedicated to Exploitation alone) is an eligible and tested mechanism, to systematically apply contractual flexibility, with additional time **after** the main R&D deliverable are completed. Free of responsibility of the main deliverables, consortia are more likely to focus on exploitation as a project within the project.

RECOMMENDATIONS to FUNDERS:

- f1* **OPEN PROPOSALS:** in the age of AI, and in broader support of EC's commitment to Open Science, EC REA Project Officers can help raise awareness on benefits of, support and promote, publishing of Open Proposals as an optional "**best practices**" for RIA type Calls, in the interest of avoiding duplication, transparency, and effective clustering with other National (co-)Funding Calls in the EU and #AllAtlantic Partner Countries (while fully respecting the need for patenting, IPR & financial confidentiality). At least three precedents exist with GRECO, [AtlantECO](#) and [MISSION ATLANTIC](#), where versions of the Description of Actions is disclosed, with consortium beneficiaries themselves deciding where is the best compromise between disclosure and confidentiality.
- f2* **CLUSTERING** with relevant **concurrent proposals** broadly, is a **more systematically embedded**, default requirement in all HorizonEU Calls, with a dedicated Task for the Governance Body of the Consortium (e.g. Executive Board, Steering Group etc), or in the case of Partnerships seek to repeat BlueBIO Call 2022 example of explicitly building up named clusters of existing projects to assist traceability for REA.
- f3* **CLUSTERING** with **concurrent proposals** in the same Call (i.e. Sister Projects), is a default expected feature of all proposals **at proposal drafting stage**, in the interest of **co-design, co-delivery** and optimizing **synergies** (without making proposals co-dependent).
- f4* EC Project Officers & Financial Officers, **proactively support beneficiaries to implement contractual flexibility** (incl. RESERVE FUNDS, or other Grant Agreement eligible mechanisms) in their proposal design, to raise awareness on GA provisions that allow projects to be more agile.
- f5* **CONTRACTUAL FLEXIBILITY** is encouraged in the official Call Text in future calls, so that applicants are more aware of eligible mechanisms (e.g. **reserve funds**) and embed those in early design stage.
- f6* **RESERVE FUNDS** resources (amount determined by each Consortium) without an allocated cost category, are a recommended design feature of the proposal in order to empower concrete CLUSTERING activities, and add eligible contractual flexibility to deliver specific synergies with concurrent/sister projects (e.g. **co-supervision of students, co-delivery**, pooling of **exploitation, commercialization** and stakeholder **outreach activities**).

ⁱ EU, US, Canada launch Atlantic Ocean research alliance (Galway Statement)

https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_13_459

ⁱⁱ Belen Statement on Atlantic Research & Innovation Cooperation (Jul 2017) https://www.aircentre.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/belem_statement_2017_en.pdf

ⁱⁱⁱ Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance CSA <http://www.atlanticresource.org/>

^{iv} All Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance Flagship, Horizon 2020 [BG-08-2018-2019 Portfolio](#) of 6 Projects over 2 years.

^v "Sister Projects" is a frequently used reference to project funded from the same Call, whether they are in direct competition, or address the identical Call but in different regions/themes.

^{vi} Sustainable harvesting of marine biological resources, Horizon 2020 [LC-BG-03-2018 Portfolio](#) of 2 Projects

^{vii} Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Technology_readiness_level

^{viii} Special report 08/2024: EU Artificial intelligence ambition – Stronger governance and increased, more focused investment essential going forward (<https://www.eca.europa.eu/en/publications/SR-2024-08>)

^{ix} Grant Agreement 862428 under H2020- BG-08-2018-2019

^x Reed et al. 2021. [Evaluating impact from research: A methodological framework](#), Research Policy 50,4, May 2021

^{xi} Proposal ASSET "Reserve Funds for Training, Mobility & Exploitation", by #AllAtlantic Project MISSION ATLANTIC (Portfolio H2020-BG-08-2018-2019), DOI:10.5281/zenodo.735140XYZ

^{xii} Early Career Ocean Professional (ECOP) Network Programme, <https://www.ecopdecade.org/>

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Contributing Projects: #AllAtlantic Project Managers Cluster drawing on these projects, the real Seven Sisters:
Astral, AquaVitae, TriATLAS, iAtlantic, SUMMER, MEESO, EuroSEAS

All Contributors shared generously with perspectives and experience from multitude of contracts across several discipline clusters, and two EC Framework Programmes, 2014-2025. You are the shining stars here!

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